

A Replication Package of “Symptoms of Architecture Erosion in Code Reviews: A Study of Two OpenStack Projects”

Ruiyin Li^{1,2}, Mohamed Soliman², Peng Liang^{1*}, Paris Avgeriou²

¹ School of Computer Science, Wuhan University, Wuhan, China

² Department of Mathematics and Computing Science, University of Groningen, Groningen, The Netherlands
{ryli_cs, liangp}@whu.edu.cn, {m.a.m.soliman, p.avgeriou}@rug.nl

Abstract—Paper title. “Symptoms of architecture erosion in code reviews: A study of two OpenStack projects”, accepted for publication at the 19th IEEE International Conference on Software Architecture (ICSA), 2022.

The purpose of the research artifact. This is a replication package by which users can access the code review comments that we collected in this study. We aim to facilitate the reuse of our material and to foster further research in the direction of identification of architecture erosion symptoms.

The badge(s) you are claiming. Our replication package fits with the following badges: functional, research object reviewed, and open research object.

The technology skills assumed by the reviewer evaluating the artifact. There are no specific skills required for the evaluation of our replication package.

Specific operating systems or other environments. There are no specific operating systems are required to reproduce the results.

Index Terms—Architecture Erosion, Code Review, Open Source Software, OpenStack

I. ARTIFACT DESCRIPTION

This is the replication package (permanently stored at Zenodo [1]) of the paper entitled “symptoms of architecture erosion in code reviews: a study of two OpenStack projects”, and accepted for publication at the 19th IEEE International Conference on Software Architecture (ICSA), 2022. The replication package is available in the paper and can be publicly accessed at the link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5676037>. The first author performed the data collection and analysis process and the third author is the corresponding author.

Our replication package [1] includes the Python scripts used to automatically mine code review data from the two OpenStack projects (i.e., Nova and Neutron) between Jan 2014 and Dec 2018. Then, we built a keyword set for narrowing the search scope of data collection and analysis and improved the keywords through following the iterative approach proposed by Bosu *et al.* [2]. The overview of the data collection and analysis process is shown in Figure 2 and the associated keywords are presented in Table II of our paper [3].

Our replication package offers Python scripts to help researchers and practitioners mine code review data from the open-source projects in the OpenStack community¹. Besides,

we provide scripts to implement the approach proposed by Bosu *et al.* [2], which can facilitate the search process of identifying architecture erosion symptoms. Employing the scripts to filter out a large number of irrelevant code review comments is the prerequisite of our research process, which helps to narrow the scope and save time for retrieving relevant code review comments. The final data in the replication package were obtained through further manual checks. Our study indicates that the proportion of the discussions on architecture erosion symptoms is rather low in code reviews (i.e., 2.4%, 502 out of 21,274 review comments). The main benefits of our replication package are that researchers and practitioners can (1) employ the scripts to mine code review comments from open-source projects in the OpenStack community, and (2) leverage the implemented approach of Bosu *et al.* [2] to build keywords for narrowing the search scope. Researchers can adapt the approach according to their research needs and scenarios to search and mine relevant textual information from code reviews.

II. AVAILABLE FILES

The replication package contains: (1) two zip files (i.e., Data.zip, Scripts.zip) with the data and scripts used in our paper, (2) the camera-ready version of our paper for ICSA 2022 (i.e., li2022sae.pdf), and (3) the remaining specification files (i.e., README.pdf, LICENCE, and STATUS.txt).

(1) **Data.zip** includes the results of data labeling and analysis.

- *Code review comments (Nova).xlsx* contains the extracted data from Nova and *Code review comments (Nova).docx* contains the related code review discussion threads on architecture erosion symptoms;
- *Code review comments (Neutron).xlsx* contains the extracted data from Neutron and *Code review comments (Neutron).docx* contains the related code review discussion threads on architecture erosion symptoms;
- *Classification of erosion symptoms.xlsx* contains the complete classification results of RQ1.

(2) **Scripts.zip** includes the Python scripts used to collect data and refine keywords.

- *get_comments.py* and *get_changes.py* are used to collect code review comments and the status of code changes, respectively.

¹ <https://www.openstack.org/>

- *keywords_stemming.py* is used to generate the word stem of each token in the keyword set (i.e., *keywords.txt*); *keywords_improve.py* is used to produce a document-term matrix for yielding co-occurring additional words; *keywords_search.py* aims at searching the comments that contain at least one keyword and *tools.py* is the middleware for searching code review data.

- (3) **li2022sac.pdf** is the camera-ready version of our paper [3] for ICSE 2022.
- (4) **LICENCE**. We use the GNU General Public License (GNU GPL).
- (5) **STATUS.txt** describes the badges we want to apply for (i.e., ROR and ORO).

III. PREREQUISITES

No specific skills are required for the evaluation of our replication package. The scripts can be run in a Python Integrated Development Environment (IDE) (e.g., PyCharm). This is a list of tools, libraries, and modules that are required to run the scripts of our paper:

- Python 3
- MongoDB (<https://www.mongodb.com/>)
- The required Python modules:
 - requests
 - json
 - pymongo
 - random
 - os
 - xlrd
 - xlwt
 - sklearn
 - nltk

IV. REPRODUCTION

1. Download this package and unzip it. Prepare the required libraries in any operating system that supports the prerequisites (see Section III). We recommend Microsoft Windows 11 or 10 operating system and PyCharm IDE.
2. Download and install modules and tools in the Prerequisites section (see Section III).
3. Run the Python scripts in PyCharm IDE. Or run the Python scripts in the folder using: `python3 *script_name*.py`. First, run *get_comments.py* and *get_changes.py* to collect code review data.
4. Run *keywords_stemming.py* to get key word stems and run *keywords_improve.py* to get a document-term matrix for the improving keyword set (if any).
5. Run *keywords_search.py* to get code review comments that contain at least one keyword.
6. Note that, the final results (i.e., *Data.zip*) of the relevant code review comments related to architecture erosion symptoms were obtained by the manual check. The results of the figures in our paper were plotted by Microsoft Excel.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Li, M. Soliman, P. Liang, and P. Avgeriou, "Replication Package for the Paper: Symptoms of Architecture Erosion in Code Reviews: A Study of Two OpenStack Projects." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5676037>, 2021.
- [2] A. Bosu, J. C. Carver, M. Hafiz, P. Hilley, and D. Janni, "Identifying the characteristics of vulnerable code changes: An empirical study," in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering (FSE)*. Hong Kong, China: ACM, 2014, pp. 257–268.
- [3] R. Li, M. Soliman, P. Liang, and P. Avgeriou, "Symptoms of Architecture Erosion in Code Reviews: A Study of Two OpenStack Projects," in *Proceedings of the 19th IEEE International Conference on Software Architecture (ICSA)*. Honolulu, Hawaii, USA: IEEE, 2022.